

MEDICAL SCIENCES

QUALITY OF DISTAL BITE TREATMENT IN CHILDREN WITH NASAL BREATHING DISORDERS

Mehmani Ilham Gasanaga

Doctor of Philosophy in Medical assistant

Department of Orthodontics

Rustamov Elshan Anvar

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Mehmani Vusala Rasim

Department of Orthodontics, assistant

Department of Orthodontics

Azerbaijan Medical University

Baku, Azerbaijan

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Nasal breathing difficulties are a triggering factor in the development of morphofunctional changes in the craniofacial region, which, if not corrected in time, can lead to dental and jaw abnormalities. The habit of mouth breathing has the most detrimental effect on the formation of the craniofacial skeleton. Mouth breathing causes the oral and pharyngeal mucous membranes to dry out, making them more susceptible to inflammation and infection by airborne bacteria. The inflammatory process gradually spreads to the pharyngeal tonsils, which normally serve as an immune defense but, due to chronic inflammation, themselves become a source of infection. Hypertrophy of the pharyngeal tonsils leads to further narrowing of the upper and lower airways and chronic hypoxia, negatively impacting the overall development of the child's body. Predisposing factors for mouth breathing in children include the specific development characteristics of the respiratory organs. If a child has nasal breathing difficulties due to chronic tonsillitis or allergic rhinitis, they inevitably develop a habit of mouth breathing, which severely affects the morphology and development of the dentofacial system. Underdevelopment of the lower jaw makes it difficult to close the lips, solidifying the mouth breathing habit. The lower lip then positions itself between the upper and lower front teeth, which contributes to the formation of distal occlusion, characterized by the protrusion of the upper incisors. Thus, there is a close pathogenic relationship between dentofacial abnormalities and nasal obstruction syndrome. Attempts to restore adequate nasal breathing solely through an otolaryngologist's intervention often do not resolve the disrupted myofunctional status, making additional diagnostic and therapeutic measures by other specialists necessary. From a practical perspective, most researchers agree that restoring airflow in the upper respiratory tract alone does not normalize the morphofunctional status of a child's craniofacial region. This circumstance necessitates early orthodontic treatment aimed at correcting dentofacial deformities and preventing skeletal-level pathologies.

Objective of the Study:

To assess the effect of removable orthodontic appliances on correcting the position of the lower jaw in treating distal occlusion in children with nasal breathing disorders.

Materials and Methods:

Examinations and treatments were conducted at the Department of Orthodontics and Dental Prosthetics of Tashkent State Dental Institute. The study involved 29 children aged 8–14, who underwent clinical, anthropometric, radiological, and photometric assessments. Inclusion criteria included growing patients with incomplete bone growth, mixed dentition, Angle Class II malocclusion, and mouth breathing. Patients were divided into three groups: Group 1 included patients with distal occlusion, mixed dentition, and a sagittal gap of less than 2 mm before treatment. Group 2 included patients with a sagittal gap up to 5 mm, and Group 3 included those with a sagittal gap between 5 and 10 mm. Individual removable plate appliances (RPAs) with inclined planes for forward movement of the lower jaw were fabricated for each patient. Mechanical components like springs (handle-shaped and protracting) and screws were included as needed.

Results:

External examination of patients revealed forward head posture relative to the spinal column, posture issues, facial asymmetry, an increased lower facial third, convex profile, and lips that did not meet. Lateral cephalometric radiographs showed increased lower facial height, vertical jaw growth with an increased mandibular angle, shortened posterior facial height, mandibular retrognathia, increased ANB angle, and narrowing of the upper airway space. In Group 1, sagittal gaps were resolved in 25 (85.7%) patients with habitual mouth breathing; however, 4 (24.7%) patients showed no change in the sagittal gap. In Group 2, 22 (75.3%) patients achieved closure of the sagittal gap after treatment, while 7 (24.7%) still had a remaining gap.

In Group 3, complete closure of the sagittal gap was not achieved. The sagittal gap was reduced to 3–4 mm in 25 (88.1%) patients, to 5–6 mm in 3 (7.1%), and to 7–8 mm in 1 (2.0%). These outcomes in Group 3 were attributed to habitual mouth breathing, pronounced mandibular retrognathia before treatment, and the inability of patients to move the lower jaw over such a large distance (6–10 mm). Patients with insufficient sagittal gap correction were referred for myotherapy and continued orthodontic treatment with removable orthodontic appliances. A follow-up examination was conducted after 1–3 months. Myogymnastic exercises

positively influenced the lower jaw position in patients with sagittal gaps of 1-6 mm after using removable orthodontic appliances. Following the use of removable orthodontic appliances with an inclined plane on the anterior part of the upper jaw, 17 (60.2%) children across all three groups showed a reduction in the sagittal gap to 2 mm or complete resolution. Three months after performing myogymnastic exercises, the sagittal gap was reduced to 2 mm or completely eliminated in 24 (83.8%) patients, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining RPAs with myogymnastics.

Conclusion:

For patients with distal occlusion and nasal breathing disorders with a sagittal gap greater than 3 mm, comprehensive treatment using removable orthodontic appliances followed by a course of myogymnastic exercises, as well as consultation with an otolaryngologist, is recommended.

References:

1. Nigmatov P.H., Nigmatova I.M., Khojayan A.Yu. Primary Adentia in Children with Mixed Dentition and Providing Dental Care // 1st International Conference of Dentists. - Tashkent, 2017, - pp. 261-262.
2. Nigmatov R.N., Nigmatova I.M., Inagamova F.K., et al. Prevalence of Speech Disorders with Dentofacial System Anomalies in Children During Mixed Dentition in Tashkent // Relevant Issues in Dentistry: Proceedings of the International Scientific-Practical Conference. - St. Petersburg, 2019. - pp. 54-62.
3. Satygo E.A. The Influence of Soft Tissue Dysfunctions on the Formation of the Dentofacial System in Children and the Possibilities of Early Correction Using Standard Myofunctional Appliances. - M.: Vallex M, 2004. - 32 pages.
4. Kumar T.V., Kuriakose S. Ultrasonographic Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Circumoral Muscle Exercises in Children // J. Clin. Pediatr. Dent. - 2004. - Vol. 29.
5. Lessa E.C., Enoki C., Feres M.F. Influence of Breathing Mode on Craniofacial Development // Otorhinolaryngol. - 2005. - Vol. 71.